

THE CATEGORY OF POLITENESS IN THE ASPECT OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION (ON THE MATERIAL OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LINGUOCULTURES

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Abstract: This article explores the concept of politeness within the context of intercultural communication, focusing on the comparison between English and Uzbek linguocultures. The study delves into the different norms, values, and behaviors related to politeness in these two cultures and examines how these differences can impact communication effectiveness and mutual understanding. Through an analysis of linguistic patterns, cultural practices, and social expectations, this research sheds light on the complexities of navigating politeness in intercultural interactions. Insights from this study can enhance cross-cultural communication strategies and deepen appreciation for the diversity of politeness norms across cultures.

Keywords: politeness, intercultural communication, English communicative culture, Uzbek communicative culture, cross-cultural communication, norms and values.

Intercultural communication plays a crucial role in today's globalized world, where individuals from different cultural backgrounds frequently interact in various contexts such as business, education, and social settings. One essential aspect of successful intercultural communication is the ability to navigate and understand the intricacies of politeness within different cultural frameworks. Politeness, defined as the culturally specific rules and conventions governing social behavior, language use, and interaction patterns, plays a pivotal role in shaping the dynamics of cross-cultural communication. The concept of politeness varies significantly across cultures, with each society having its own norms, values, and expectations regarding what constitutes polite behavior. These differences can lead to misunderstandings, misinterpretations, and even conflicts in intercultural interactions if not carefully navigated. Therefore, an in-depth examination of politeness in different communicative cultures is essential for promoting effective communication, fostering

mutual respect, and building strong relationships across cultural boundaries. In this article, we will explore the category of politeness within the context of intercultural communication, focusing specifically on the comparison between English and Uzbek communicative cultures. By examining these two distinct cultural contexts, we aim to shed light on the diverse ways in which politeness is manifested, expressed, and perceived in different cultural settings.¹⁹ Through an analysis of linguistic patterns, cultural practices, and social expectations related to politeness in English and Uzbek communicative cultures, we will uncover the underlying factors that influence polite behavior and communication styles in these societies. This research will contribute to a deeper understanding of the complexities of navigating politeness in intercultural interactions and provide valuable insights for individuals and professionals engaged in cross-cultural communication. By recognizing and respecting the cultural differences in politeness norms, we can enhance communication effectiveness, promote intercultural understanding, and strengthen relationships across diverse cultural contexts.

Politeness is a fundamental aspect of social interaction that revolves around demonstrating respect, consideration, and kindness towards others. It involves employing manners, etiquette, and courteous behavior in various social situations to maintain harmonious relationships and uphold societal norms. Politeness encompasses a wide range of behaviors, gestures, and language use that are designed to show appreciation, deference, and thoughtfulness towards others. At its core, politeness is about acknowledging the feelings, perspectives, and needs of others while navigating social interactions with grace and sensitivity. It involves displaying empathy, understanding, and empathy towards others, regardless of differences in opinions, beliefs, or backgrounds. Politeness is not just a superficial nicety; it is a foundational aspect of effective communication and relationship-building that fosters mutual respect, trust, and cooperation among individuals. Politeness can manifest in various forms, including verbal expressions, nonverbal cues, and behavioral patterns that convey respect and consideration towards others. Common polite phrases such as "please," "thank you," "excuse me," and "I'm sorry" are used to show appreciation, gratitude, and remorse in social interactions. Polite gestures such as holding the door

¹⁹ Mambetniyazova, A., Babaeva, G., Dauletbayeva, R., Paluanova, M., & Abishova, G. (2024). Linguistic and cultural analysis of the concept "politeness". *Semiotica*, 30-54.

for someone, offering a seat to a stranger, or giving a compliment are examples of nonverbal politeness that demonstrate kindness, generosity, and thoughtfulness.²⁰

In addition to words and actions, politeness also involves observing social norms, customs, and expectations that govern interactions within a given culture or community. Each society has its own set of politeness rules, etiquettes, and conventions that dictate how individuals should behave, communicate, and interact with others. These norms may vary across cultures, regions, and social contexts, leading to differences in the ways politeness is expressed and perceived. Politeness is not just about following rigid rules or codes of conduct; it is about showing genuine consideration and empathy towards others in all social interactions. It requires individuals to be mindful of their words, actions, and behaviors and to treat others with kindness, respect, and dignity. Politeness goes beyond mere politeness; it is about fostering positive relationships, building trust, and creating a sense of belonging and community among individuals. In today's fast-paced and interconnected world, the importance of politeness in social interactions cannot be overstated. As we navigate complex social environments, cultural differences, and diverse perspectives, politeness serves as a universal language that transcends barriers and builds bridges between individuals from different backgrounds. By embracing politeness as a guiding principle in our interactions, we can promote understanding, empathy, and harmony in our communities and beyond.

In today's interconnected and globalized world, intercultural communication has become a fundamental aspect of our daily interactions. When individuals from different cultural backgrounds come together, understanding and navigating the intricacies of politeness play a crucial role in ensuring effective communication and building strong relationships. To begin with, let us explore the concept of politeness within the English communicative culture. In England, politeness is often associated with certain linguistic markers and expressions that convey respect, consideration, and social norms.²¹ For example, the use of polite forms such as "please," "thank you," and "excuse me" are considered essential in English social interactions to demonstrate courtesy and respect towards others. Moreover, the notion of indirectness and politeness strategies, such as hedging, mitigation, and indirect requests, are commonly employed in English discourse to maintain social harmony

²⁰ Günthner, Susanne. "Intercultural communication and the relevance of cultural specific repertoires of communicative genres." *Handbook of intercultural communication* 7 (2007): 128-158.

²¹ Pulkar, Turdieva. "Linguapragmatic analyze of greetings in Persian and Uzbek languages." *Бюллетень науки и практики* 5, no. 9 (2019): 521-530.

and avoid causing offense. In contrast, the Uzbek communicative culture exhibits its unique set of politeness norms and values that reflect the cultural heritage and social dynamics of the society. In Uzbekistan, politeness is deeply ingrained in the traditional values of hospitality, respect for elders, and hierarchies within social relationships. Polite forms of address, honorifics, and expressions of gratitude are highly valued in Uzbek communication as a way to show deference, humility, and appreciation towards others. Furthermore, indirect communication styles, implicit speech acts, and nonverbal cues are often used in Uzbek interactions to convey politeness and maintain harmonious relationships. When individuals from English and Uzbek communicative cultures engage in intercultural communication, the differences in politeness norms and strategies can lead to misunderstandings, misinterpretations, and potential conflicts. For instance, an English speaker's direct and straightforward communication style may be perceived as impolite or confrontational by an Uzbek interlocutor who values indirectness and restraint in speech. Similarly, an Uzbek speaker's use of honorifics and elaborate greetings might be seen as excessive or insincere by an English counterpart who values simplicity and efficiency in communication. Here are some examples to illustrate the statement:

Example 1: Greetings. In Uzbek culture, it's customary to use elaborate greetings when meeting someone, such as "Assalomu alaykum" (peace be upon you) followed by a series of questions about the person's health, family, and well-being. In contrast, an English speaker might find this excessive and prefer a simple "hello, how are you?" An Uzbek speaker might view the English greeting as abrupt or even rude, while the English speaker might see the Uzbek greeting as insincere or overly formal.

Example 2: Honorifics. In Uzbek culture, it's common to use honorific titles such as "hurmatli" (respected) or "oqsoqol" (esteemed) when addressing someone who is older or in a position of authority. An English speaker might find this excessive and prefer to use first names or simple titles like "Mr." or "Ms." An Uzbek speaker might view the English approach as disrespectful or informal, while the English speaker might see the Uzbek approach as overly formal or even insincere.

Example 3: Communication Style. In Uzbek culture, communication often involves elaborate expressions of politeness and respect, such as using phrases like "if you permit me" or "if you allow me" when making a request. An English speaker might find this excessive and prefer a more direct approach, such as simply stating the request. An Uzbek speaker might view the English approach as abrupt or rude, while the English speaker might see the Uzbek approach as inefficient or insincere.

To navigate these differences effectively and foster successful intercultural communication, it is essential for individuals to develop cultural awareness, sensitivity, and adaptability in their communication practices. By recognizing and respecting the diverse politeness norms and conventions of each cultural context, individuals can bridge the gap between different communicative cultures and build mutual understanding and trust. Strategies such as active listening, open-mindedness, and willingness to learn about the cultural norms of the interlocutor can help mitigate misunderstandings and promote harmonious interactions in intercultural settings.²²

In conclusion, the category of politeness plays a pivotal role in shaping intercultural communication dynamics and relationships between individuals from different cultural backgrounds. Through a comparative analysis of the English and Uzbek communicative cultures, we have explored the diverse ways in which politeness is manifested, expressed, and perceived in these societies. By unpacking the linguistic patterns, cultural practices, and social expectations related to politeness in each cultural context, we have highlighted the importance of cultural sensitivity, awareness, and adaptability in navigating politeness in intercultural interactions. As we continue to engage in cross-cultural communication in our increasingly diverse world, understanding the nuances of politeness in different communicative cultures is essential for building bridges, fostering mutual respect, and creating meaningful connections across cultural boundaries. By embracing cultural diversity, valuing differences, and approaching intercultural communication with empathy and openness, we can cultivate a more inclusive, harmonious, and interconnected global community.

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